

FORMULATING AN EFFECTIVE STRAIN ENERGY RELEASE RATE FOR A LINEAR ELASTIC FRACTURE MECHANICS DESCRIPTION OF DELAMINATION GROWTH

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SUMMARY

Although the use of strain energy release rate for characterizing fatigue delamination growth behaviour in composites is common, consensus has not been reached on formulating an effective strain energy release rate parameter. This paper demonstrates that a logical formulation for such a parameter exists, based on linear elastic fracture mechanics and the principle of similitude.

Keywords: Strain energy release rate, delamination growth;

INTRODUCTION

The study and characterization of delamination growth behaviour has gained significant attention in the research community due to the growing use of composite structures in a wide range of structural applications. A widely utilized approach is to apply a linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) description using the strain energy release rate (G) in a manner analogous to crack growth in terms of the stress intensity factor (K). The primary reason for the use of G rather than K is that the local crack-tip stresses used to determine K are difficult to obtain in inhomogeneous composite laminates. Use of G avoids the need to determine crack-tip stresses. Using this analogy, delamination growth rate (db/dN) can be characterized using a Paris Law relation:

$$\frac{db}{dN} = C_d (G_{eff})^{n_d} \quad (1)$$

In applying this description for delamination growth under cyclic loading, however, there is a lack of consensus on the formulation of G_{eff} . Two of the more common formulations are to replace G_{eff} by the maximum strain energy release rate, G_{max} [1, 2], or by the difference in maximum and minimum values of G , $\Delta G = G_{max} - G_{min}$ [3]. The prevalent use of G_{max} stems from the importance of this parameter in assessing static failure limits. The drawback of its use for fatigue is that it does not contain any information about the minimum load, and is thus dependent on the applied load ratio, R . The use of $\Delta G = G_{max} - G_{min}$ attempts to remedy this by using the applied strain energy release rate range; however, it violates the rules of superposition for G , thus it unsuccessfully removes the R ratio dependency.

The selection of a formulation for G_{eff} should not be so arbitrary. It is not simply a curve fitting parameter for experimental data sets. By reviewing linear elastic fracture mechanics theory, this paper seeks to demonstrate that a logical formulation for G_{eff} exists. Using this formulation, it will be demonstrated that effects such as R-ratio dependency for Mode II delamination growth and residual stress effects can be removed.

LEFM AND THE SIMILITUDE PRINCIPLE

The basis for fatigue crack growth prediction in LEFM theory is the relation of crack growth rate (da/dN) to the stress intensity factor range (ΔK), and the application of the similitude principle. The stress intensity factor is a measure of the stress and strain field ahead of the crack tip. Application of the similitude principle assumes that for the same variation in the stress and strain field ahead of the crack tip (same ΔK), the same crack growth rate will occur. Thus, using ΔK as a fracture parameter, the crack growth rate can be predicted using the empirical observed Paris Law relation:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = C(\Delta K)^n \quad (2)$$

A few remarks need to be made regarding the use of ΔK as a similitude parameter. As K is an elastic parameter, similitude in reality can be violated by the presence of gross plasticity and other non-linear elastic effects that can occur. In general, ΔK is still used with the addition of corrections to account for the non-linear elastic behaviours, such as plasticity induced crack closure.

LEFM STRAIN ENERGY RELEASE RATE DESCRIPTION

The strain energy release rate, G , is equal to the total amount of elastic energy made available for crack (or delamination) extension per unit increase in crack surface area. Written as an energy balance:

$$G = \frac{d}{db}(F - \Delta U) \quad (3)$$

where F and ΔU are the work applied to the system and increase in elastic energy of the system respectively, both as a result of an extension of the delamination by length b .

Use of the strain energy release rate as a LEFM parameter, instead of K , for delamination growth in composite materials stems from the difficulty in determining the local crack tip stress field in orthotropic laminates needed for calculating K . Calculation of the strain energy release rate in such cases is more simple than K , and since it is based on the same underlying LEFM assumptions, it can be related to K . Although the exact relationship can depend on the loading mode and level of constraint in the system (plane stress – plane strain), $G \propto K^2$ [4, 5].

Reformulating the LEFM fracture parameter, ΔK , in terms of G based on the above proportionality results in the following:

$$\Delta K \propto \left(\sqrt{G_{\max}} - \sqrt{G_{\min}} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

Despite this, it is common for the adoption of $\Delta G = G_{\max} - G_{\min}$ to be made, assuming an analogy with ΔK for crack growth. Simply taking the arithmetic difference in strain energy release rate is not equivalent to the difference in stress intensity factor.

Another way to illustrate this is to consider the rules of superposition for strain energy release rate. For a linear elastic system, there is no interaction between the different modes of deformation (Mode I, II, and III), thus the total strain energy release rate for a given system is the arithmetic sum of the strain energy release rates for the individual deformation modes:

$$G_T = G_I + G_{II} + G_{III} \quad (5)$$

However, when considering the superposition of strain energy release rates resulting from the same deformation mode, the rules for superposition are as follows [6]:

$$\begin{aligned} G_I &= \left[\sqrt{G_{I(1)}} + \sqrt{G_{I(2)}} + \sqrt{G_{I(3)}} + \dots \right]^2 \\ G_{II} &= \left[\sqrt{G_{II(1)}} + \sqrt{G_{II(2)}} + \sqrt{G_{II(3)}} + \dots \right]^2 \\ G_{III} &= \left[\sqrt{G_{III(1)}} + \sqrt{G_{III(2)}} + \sqrt{G_{III(3)}} + \dots \right]^2 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Thus, when expressing the strain energy release rate range for a given deformation mode, ΔG should not be the simple arithmetic difference of G_{\max} and G_{\min} , but should be formulated as follows for a given deformation mode:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G_I &= \left(\sqrt{G_{I\max}} - \sqrt{G_{I\min}} \right)^2 \\ \Delta G_T &= \Delta G_I + \Delta G_{II} + \Delta G_{III} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

A simple way to illustrate the impact of using $\Delta G = G_{\max} - G_{\min}$ vs. $(\sqrt{G_{\max}} - \sqrt{G_{\min}})^2$ is to consider a case where delamination behaviour for two load ratios are obtained for the same crack/specimen geometry. For this illustration, we will consider a double cantilever beam (DCB) specimen with a delamination crack length, b , and specimen width, B . For such a specimen, the Mode I strain energy release rate can be determined by [5]:

$$G_I = \frac{P^2}{2B} \frac{dC}{db} \quad (8)$$

where P is the applied load and C is the compliance of the DCB specimen. If the crack and specimen geometries are identical, then the specimen compliance is the same, the crack tip stress field (characterized by K) is only a function of applied load, and differences in G_I are influenced by the square of the applied load only.

If we consider this simple DCB example and determine ΔG using $G_{\max} - G_{\min}$ and $(\sqrt{G_{\max}} - \sqrt{G_{\min}})^2$, for the case $P_{\max} = P_{\max}$, and $R = 0$, then determine the corresponding stress amplitude that will produce the same ΔG for an R-ratio of 0.3, the results illustrated in Figure 1 are obtained. Using $\Delta G = G_{\max} - G_{\min}$, the resultant stress amplitude and mean stress are influenced by R-ratio, while for $\Delta G = (\sqrt{G_{\max}} - \sqrt{G_{\min}})^2$, the applied stress amplitude remains the same (similitude is preserved).

Figure 1: Schematic of the applied stress amplitudes for a constant dC/db and ΔG using arithmetic and superposition definitions of ΔG .

BENEFITS OF A SUPERPOSITION BASED SERR RANGE

In the previous section, it was illustrated that using a SERR range, ΔG , based on the rules of superposition for G preserves similitude of the crack tip stress field range (and thus applied stress range for identical crack/specimen geometries). Within this section, some of the benefits of this property for characterizing delamination growth behaviour under fatigue loading will be examined.

Stress Ratio Effects

Based on the principle of similitude and LEFM theory, delamination growth behaviour is expected to be the same for different stress ratios as long as the similitude parameter ($\Delta G = (\sqrt{G_{\max}} - \sqrt{G_{\min}})^2$) is conserved. This also applies for crack growth where similar crack growth rates are expected for the same ΔK value. Experience has shown that this, however, is not the case for Mode I crack growth in metals. A distinct influence of R -ratio is observed. This influence for Mode I crack growth can be related to a physical mechanism, crack closure, which is a non linear elastic behaviour, and thus a violation of LEFM assumptions. Rather than dismissing LEFM in this case, it is common to continue using the similitude parameter, ΔK , and correct it for closure effects.

This approach has also been adopted for characterizing delamination growth. If a variation in behaviour is observed related to stress ratio, it is corrected using an empirical correction factor, often without the rigorous mechanistic explanation for the stress ratio dependency as developed for Mode I crack growth in metals. Some of the variations observed in the literature, however, are due to the use of $\Delta G = G_{\max} - G_{\min}$ as the characterization parameter, and the violation of similitude that accompanies it. For instance, consider delamination growth along an interface growing under Mode II conditions only. No closure effects should be expected under Mode II loading as deformation occurs parallel to the fracture plane rather than perpendicular. However, when plotting fatigue delamination growth rate (db/dN) behaviour under Mode II

loading as in Figure 2a for aluminium aramid-epoxy fibre metal laminates (FMLs), an apparent stress ratio effect is observed. When plotted using the correct definition of ΔG which preserves similitude, the apparent stress ratio effect disappears (Figure 2b).

Figure 2: Comparison of stress ratio effects for Mode II delamination growth behaviour using $\Delta G = G_{max} - G_{min}$ (a) and $(\sqrt{G_{max}} - \sqrt{G_{min}})^2$ (b), based on data obtained from [7].

Figure 3: Comparison of influence of ΔG definition on Mode I DCB delamination growth data in unidirectional carbon-epoxy laminates for an R-ratio of 0.35 and differing opening displacements.

Even in cases where stress ratio effects may be present, the use of $\Delta G = (\sqrt{G_{max}} - \sqrt{G_{min}})^2$ can improve the fit and usability of delamination growth data. Mode I DCB delamination growth tests in unidirection carbon-epoxy laminates performed by Khan [8] showed that a stress ratio effect was indeed present in his tests, even when using $\Delta G = (\sqrt{G_{max}} - \sqrt{G_{min}})^2$. However, in one particular test series, Khan ran delamination tests at the same stress ratio, but with different initial DCB opening displacements (different applied stress range for the same delamination crack length). When plotting the results from this test series, Khan found that the use of $\Delta G = G_{max} - G_{min}$ as a characterization

parameter resulted in two distinct curves for the single stress ratio (Figure 3). When using $\Delta G = (\sqrt{G_{\max}} - \sqrt{G_{\min}})^2$, however, similarity is conserved between the two data sets and the data collapses onto one trend line as shown in Figure 3b. R^2 values are shown to illustrate closeness of fit to the shown trend lines.

Residual Stress Effects

Residual stresses/strains form in composite laminates during the cooling phase after curing due to mismatches in the thermal coefficients of expansion amongst the layers of the laminate. Several studies have investigated the effects of residual stress on delamination growth behaviour and have developed numerous parameters and methods for accounting for their effects [7, 9-12]. The presence of a residual stress, however, can simply be viewed as a modification of the means stress, or stress ratio, for the fatigue loading case because it is present during the whole applied load cycle. Thus, as demonstrated in the previous section, use of $\Delta G = G_{\max} - G_{\min}$ to characterize the influence of residual stress will result in an apparent effect due to the violation of similitude.

If $\Delta G = (\sqrt{G_{\max}} - \sqrt{G_{\min}})^2$ is used to characterize the effect of residual stress on delamination growth is used, it is easily shown that the residual stress component of the strain energy release rate is removed. If the total strain energy release rate, G , is broken up into a component due to the residual stress (G_r) and a component due to the applied loads (G_{applied}), then:

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta G &= (\sqrt{G_{\max}} - \sqrt{G_{\min}})^2 \\ &= \left[(\sqrt{G_{\text{applied},\max}} + \sqrt{G_r}) - (\sqrt{G_{\text{applied},\min}} + \sqrt{G_r}) \right]^2 \\ &= (\sqrt{G_{\text{applied},\max}} - \sqrt{G_{\text{applied},\min}})^2\end{aligned}\quad (9)$$

This removal of the residual stress component of the strain energy release rate is convenient as it is often difficult to accurately determine the residual stress state due to the limited accuracy of the coefficients of thermal expansion used to determine it. Thus, for fatigue delamination propagation purposes, they can be omitted from the analysis. In making such an omission, it should be remembered that the inclusion of the residual stress component of G can not be omitted when considering static failure. Additionally, in materials/loading modes where the stress ratio has an effect on fatigue delamination growth behaviour, the change in stress ratio resulting from the residual stress state should be taken into account.

The power of this can be illustrated using Mode II fatigue delamination growth data obtained by Lin and Kao for various aluminum carbon-epoxy FMLs [12]. In their work, Lin and Kao tested laminates consisting of two aluminum layers with a unidirectional carbon-epoxy core. Three core configurations were tested, consisting of 2, 4, and 6 carbon-epoxy prepreg sheets (designated C2, C4, and C6 respectively), resulting in three different residual curing stress states. In addition to testing laminates in the as cured condition, specimens that had been post stretched (producing plastic strains in the metal layers to balance the thermal residual strains) to remove the residual stresses were also tested.

Figure 4: Comparison of residual stress effects on Mode II delamination growth behaviour using $\Delta G = G_{\max} - G_{\min}$ (a) and $(\sqrt{G_{\max}} - \sqrt{G_{\min}})^2$ (b), based on data obtained from [9-12].

Figure 5: Schematic of delamination test specimen with strain and displacement nomenclature (containing no residual stress) adapted from [12].

Results from Lin and Kao are plotted in Figure 4. To determine the strain energy release rate, Lin and Kao used the following:

$$G = \frac{1}{w} \left[P \left(\frac{d\delta}{db} \right) - \frac{dU}{db} \right] \quad (10)$$

where db is the increment in delamination length, w is the width of the specimen, and $d\delta$ is the change in deflection of the specimen resulting from db (see Figure 5). The work and strain energy terms can be further broken down as follows:

$$\frac{d\delta}{db} = \varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_2 \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{dU}{db} = w \left[\frac{\sigma_{1c}^2}{2E_c} t_c - \left(\frac{\sigma_{2c}^2}{2E_c} t_c + \frac{\sigma_{2a}^2}{2E_a} t_a \right) \right] \quad (12)$$

where the subscripts c and a refer to the composite and aluminum layers respectively, E is the Young's modulus, t is the layer thickness, ε is the applied layer strain, σ is the layer stress, and subscripts 1 and 2 refer to regions 1 and 2 in Figure 5.

In order to incorporate the residual curing stresses, Lin and Kao calculated the layer stresses based on the applied (ε_1 and ε_2) and residual strains ($\varepsilon_{r,c}$ and $\varepsilon_{r,a}$):

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{1c} &= E_c \varepsilon_1 \\ \sigma_{2c} &= E_c (\varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_{r,c}) \\ \sigma_{2a} &= E_a (\varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_{r,a}) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Using equations 11-13, Lin and Kao determined the strain energy release rate including the effect of residual stress. This procedure, however, only included the effect of residual strain on the strain energy term (dU/db) of G . To correctly determine G including residual strains, eqn. 11 must include the residual strain component such that:

$$\frac{d\delta}{db} = (\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_2) + \varepsilon_{r,c} \quad (14)$$

This correction was implemented into the data set given in Figure 4.

In Figure 4a, the *as cured* tests show an apparent residual stress effect on the Mode II delamination growth behaviour when characterized using $\Delta G = G_{\max} - G_{\min}$. When characterized using $\Delta G = (\sqrt{G_{\max}} - \sqrt{G_{\min}})^2$, which preserves similitude, this apparent effect of residual stress is removed (Figure 4b). As discussed in the previous section, under Mode II loading, no apparent closure mechanisms or other mechanisms which violate the assumptions of LEFM exist, so their indeed should not be an influence of residual stress on fatigue delamination growth.

CONCLUSIONS

A new formulation for $G_{eff} = \Delta G = (\sqrt{G_{\max}} - \sqrt{G_{\min}})^2$ for describing the delamination growth behaviour of an interface using a Paris-type relation has been proposed. This formulation has been developed based on LEFM and the principle of similitude used in the establishment of ΔK for characterising crack growth in metals. This development was demonstrated by reformulating ΔK in terms of G , and by deriving the proper formulation of ΔG based on the rules of superposition for G .

The power of this new formulation has been demonstrated through several case studies. By characterizing delamination growth using $\Delta G = (\sqrt{G_{\max}} - \sqrt{G_{\min}})^2$, a more generic description of the fatigue behaviour can be obtained. In instances where mechanisms which violate LEFM assumptions are not present, the proposed formulation has been

shown to remove apparent effects due to residual stress and variations in stress ratio. Furthermore, preserving similitude with the proposed formulation was shown to reduce scatter and produce a more generic characterization of delamination growth behaviour for tests performed at the same stress ratio.

Finally, it may be argued that in adopting a Paris relation to fit experimental delamination growth data, the selection of the independent variable for fitting the data is arbitrary. It is merely an exercise in correlating experimental data. This, however, should not be the case. Applying a Paris relation is done not simply to curve fit experimental data, but to attempt to capture the material behaviour based on an assumed theory. In the case of delamination growth, that theory is linear elastic fracture mechanics. Thus, the selection of the independent variable should be based on this theory, and should conserve similitude and obey the rules of superposition outlined within it. Otherwise, efforts to characterize material behaviour are reduced to arbitrary curve fits with limited applicability and transferability.

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